

The Ideologies of Hegel, Marx, Lenin, Popper, Huntington, Fukuyama, Hayek, Friedman - in Favor of The Deep Mafia for the Enslavement of Nations, Peoples.

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³Prof Momtchil Dobrev's "MAFIOTISMUS"

"Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven MATERIALISMUS" - the real hidden ideology of the DEEP MAFIA

Does the Nobel Committee serve the deep mafia?!?!

Abstract: Lord prof PhD PhD Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev developed 2010 "Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism" as a based principle materialismus since more than 17 century.08 "Theory of generating of crises", 2010 "Theory and praxice of the Mafiotismus "And 2001" Theory of the mafia ". Based on these two theories this paper explains the establishment of mafiotismus all over the world - principles, theory and praxis we prove with the guiding article that these are the ideologies of the Deep Mafia.

Keywords: Mafiotismus, mafia, Deep Mafia, theory.

I. Introduction

In the year 2010 Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed the 'Theory of Mafiotismus' as a new state niveaou based on private and personal interests of the prime-minister, ministers, government .. Based on this "Theory of Mafiotismus" Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev developed 2010 the "Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism" as a based principle materialismus since the 17th century.

Real mafia and Financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism is the ideology of the Deep Mafia, which is synonymous with the powers that govern the world, countries, institutions from the 17th century to the present.

1.1 Introduce the Problem

Real disclosure of the causes of work, the ideology of the Deep Mafia - synonymous with the black aristocracy that ruled the world after the 17th century is important for revealing the goals, objectives, methods of world governance of this group of people and companies.

That is the purpose of this article.

1.2. The developed by Lord Prof. Dr. Momchil Dobrev Financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism and Mafia are the real ideology of Depth Mafia and its essence, principles, content.

II. Research methods

Research methods of occurrence of financially banking resource-based technological mafia-driven materialism and the MAFIOTISMUS, its logic of work, of existence, of management are the following:

- Analysis of the history
- Analysis of the wars and revolutions since 17 century
- Analysis if the ways of the financing of these wars and revolutions
- Analysis of the people, crises, institutions that are driven all the processes

- Analysis of the real process in the beginning of wars, the process of the wars and the revolutions, the financing of the parts participants in the wars and revolutions.
- Analysis of the laws of one country.
- Analysis of all authorities in one country - judicial, legislative, executive
- Analysis of the implementation of the laws of a country
- Analysis of management of public affairs
- Analysis of the existence and / or presence of civil society.
- Analysis of the work of the Prosecutor's Office as a guarantor of the existence and development of mobbing.
- Analysis of the social directions of development of a society
- Analysis of the judiciary - laws, judges, choice of judges, development of judges, violations of judges, disciplinary and other liability of judges, prosecutors, investigators.
- Analysis of history
- Analysis of the First world war - financing, reasons
- Analysis of the Second World War - financing, reasons,
- Analysis of the French revolution - financing reasons
- Analysis of the American independence war - financing, reason
- Analysis of the establishment of the USA
- Analysis of other wars and revolutions.

III. THE DEEP MAFIA - short description, concept, content,

The deep state is a corporate, militarized, functionally defined, mafia group of people who manage and own financial, banking, corporate, IT companies, not elected by the citizens of the state, who actually govern not only a particular country but also a group of countries, on the principles of Mafia and the financial bank resource technological mafia Materialism.

The deep state has corrupted and mafiaized all spheres of society on which the governance of a country, of a union depends - in the case of the European Commission and the European Union, the United States.

Concept - Prof. Momchil Dobrev

THE DEEP STATE is an organization, structure, government, kleptocracy, and cryptocracy of a group of people from the financial banking, resource, technological, corporate elite, which works in all countries on the principles of Mafiosis and financial banking resource technological mafia Materialism.

IV. AREAS OF GOVERNANCE, CONTROL, THE DEEP STATE, THE MAFIA IN MAFIOTISMUS

The deep state can be found in all spheres of public life.

The spheres of action, management, control, manifestation of the deep state through the mafia and on the basis of the financial bank resource technological mafia materialism through the mafia are as follows:

-1/. The sphere of state administration. This includes government, prime ministers, ministers, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, their control through compromising and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

- 2/. The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non-profit associations, the degradation of the political elite, their control through compromising, and other addictions, sexual addictions and other addictions.

- 3/. The sphere of the judicial system / judges, prosecutors, investigators /, their control through addictions - bribes, gifts, excursions, knotrol through compromising, and other addictions - sexual, gambling and others.

4/. The sphere of law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /, their control through addictions, bribes, and others.

5/. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc.,

- 6/. The private sector,

- 7/. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, their control and management through racketeering, coercion, pressure, sanctions and others.

- 8/ The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

9 / . Banking and financial sector

10 / . Social networks and information technology

11 / . Control and management of the management and administration of intelligence services, intelligence agencies, internal security departments, intelligence services - space, central security services, national security services, intelligence and counterintelligence departments, intelligence departments of the Ministry of Defense, naval intelligence, air services,

12 / . Leadership and management of state treasury intelligence,

13. The overthrow of regimes through "yellow", "orange" revolutions and the appointment of governments, presidents to serve the interests of the deep state

14 / . Provoking occasions for starting and starting wars against countries whose territories with the respective natural resources are of interest to the representatives of the deep state.

15 / . Imposition of policy in the respective countries, which are of the economic interests of the deep state and their profits from it.

16 / . Imposition of a policy in the case of NATO for the purpose of threats, wars against third countries from the territories of the countries.

17 / . Imposing a global governance roar, a New World Order that will allow them to more easily govern states, nations, peoples, economies, industries, finance, capital.

18 / . Creating conditions, causing chaos with the ultimate goal of profits - economic, financial.

19 / - Management, control of the civil society, through non-governmental organizations, their financing / example SOROS / ,

20 / . Imposing their requirements on military budgets of all countries for the purpose of selling weapons from the military-industrial complex of countries, countries.

21 / . Control of criminal groups and groups

22 / . Control of trade, military, criminal groups, the defense industry, the financial sector, corporate media and counterterrorism.

23 / . Managing the military budgets of states, at least more than half goes to military spending and the purchase of equipment and weapons.

24 / . Control and management of the military-industrial complex

25 / Control and management of the state money, budgets, of the respective state

26 / . Management of many non-governmental national and international structures - the Council on Foreign Relations, the Royal Institute of International Affairs, the Trust Commission, the Bilderberg Group, the Club of Rome, the Committee of 300,

27 / . Supranational governance of the countries of the planet.

28. Governance of international institutions - UN, UNICEF, World Health Organization,

29 / . Committing crimes against people, individuals, services

30 / . Imposing globalization as an ideology

31 / . Imposing the ideology and society of lesbianism, gay, bisexual and transgender people - LGBT people as a leader at the state level.

32 / . Use of compromising control of individuals - politicians and any others on whom depends the state and other decisions responsible for the whole society.

33 / . Create a program, plan, and accomplish the task of destroying Christianity.

34 / Destruction of the family as a basic building block of society.

35 / . Targeted organization of migration through refugee waves, crises

36 / . Control and management of the electoral process in each country, imposing organization, management of the electoral process through various schemes of falsification and fraud.

37 / . Social terrorism of society from a moral, spiritual, economic point of view.

38 / . Total control of the population, by monitoring and controlling the permanent address, social activity on Facebook, Twitter, etc., driving licenses, watched or recorded movies, activity on various blogs, viewing or sending photos, detention by the police, subway trips, credit and debit cards, financial information, viewed photos, sent photos, facial recognition by surveillance cameras, sent e-mails, received emails, searching for information on the network, health card, education, train tickets, bus, plane, recorded mobile phone applications, used applications, traffic, online transactions, test messages sent, test messages received,

39 / . Terrorist acts through the state

40 / . Total control of the population, by monitoring and controlling the permanent address, social activity on Facebook, Twitter, etc., driving licenses, watched or recorded movies, activity on various blogs, viewing or sending photos, detention by the police, subway trips, credit and debit cards, financial information, viewed photos, sent photos, face recognition by surveillance cameras, sent e-mails, received emails, searching for information on the network, health

card, education, train tickets, bus, plane, recorded mobile applications, used applications, traffic, online transactions, text messages sent, and messages

41 / . Terrorist actions through the state, the United States and NATO, and other military organizations

42 / . Terrorist actions through private formations

43 / . Ruin and collapse of the education system

44 / . killing the national achievements of democracy

45 / . destruction of the social system

46 / . polarization of society

47 / . destruction of national values

48 / . destruction of the national culture

49 / . destruction of rights and freedoms

50 / . destruction of the middle class

51 / . increasing poverty and inequality

52 / . increase begging

53 / . Indebtedness of countries, governments through the IMF, WB, ECB

54 / . Dependence of the media - television, radio, newspapers, magazines,

55 / . Control, management of the drug business since the 18th century by the black aristocracy

56 / . Creating inequalities in society, managing these inequalities, destroying the middle class, with the ultimate goal of enslaving society.

57 / . Creating conditions for control and management of the economies of entire countries with the sole purpose of personal gain.

58 / . Creation of a university elite - a Masonic mafia-based global elite to rule states, and other institutions in favor of the Global Masonic elite.

59 / . Control and management of education in a country in order to blunt, greater control and management of the masses and the younger generation in order to zombie and control and control at any level - emotional, educational, social and others.

60 / . Creating a system for SOCIAL GEOCITE

61 / . Control is the management of health care with the ultimate goal of reducing the population of the planet,

62 / . Control and management of the system of drug development and dependence of the population on drugs.

63 / . Control and management of patents and developments and elimination of scientists who created discoveries that can improve people's lives.

64 / . Control and liquidate scientists, creators of drugs, but new methods of treatment that are cheap and hinder the wealth of the elite.

65 / . Control and liquidation of scientists creating systems for zero-point generators and free energy generators.

66 / . Control, management, drug production and addiction among the population with the ultimate goal of profit.

67. Control, creation of GMO products, food, for the purpose of profit and reduction of the population.

68 / . Population control and management through food, lethal medicine, lethal vaccines, psychiatric medicines, deadly food, deadly grain, deadly sweeteners, GMOs, deadly water, air,

69 / . Control and management of the media, conquest of the media, and propaganda only of their goals, ideas, aspirations, plans, disguised under the slogan that care for humanity and the people in it.

70 / . Establish institutions that will govern countries, policies, such as the UN, UNICEF and others

71 / . Control of the special and secret services through their Freemasons to serve their lodges and personal interests, but not the laws of the respective state.

72 / . Establishment of their own structures, in which their people will be members who will later govern and be heads of states - Council on Foreign Relations, 1921 and branches - Institute for Pacific Relations - New York, Center for Foreign Policy Studies - Paris, Institute for foreign policy - Hamburg, Royal Institute of International Affairs -1920, Bilberberg Group - 1954, Club of Rome - 1968, Trilateral Commission 1973, to determine the international policies of states, to govern states.

73 / . Creation of an elite by the University of Global Masonic Mafia Elite - Yale University, Harvard, Columbia, Corel University, New York University, Sarah Lawrence College, Stanford University, University of Chicago, John Copkins, Brown University,

74 / . Control and management of all Masonic lodges - Knights Templar, Freemasonry, Rosicrucians, lodge of Gnosticism, Kabbalism, the Illuminati Freemasons through the principles of the Church of Lucifer.

75/. Control and management of the elite and societies and states through Foundations - Rockefeller Foundation, Ford Foundation, Carnegie Endowment, Clinton Foundation,

76 / . Media management and control,
proprietary television - BBC, CBC, CNN, CBS, ABC, CNN and others,
telegraph agencies - the Associated Press, Reuters and others,
newspapers - New York Times, Washington Post, Wall Street Journal, Boston Globe, Baltimore Sun, Chicago Sun Times, Los Angeles Stays, Houston Post, Minneapolis Star / Tribune and others,
magazines. Fortune, Time, Life, Money, People, Newsweek, Business Week, Readers Ridge, US EU News and World Report, and others, dozens of publishers,

77 / . Propaganda and manipulation to reduce critical thinking
-- increasing the closedness, depression, dependence, feelings of slavery and dependence on the decisions and actions of the government
-- turning one's back on the real facts and evidence
-- dependence on propaganda
-- dependence on the promoted fear and stress
-- increase in mental illness
-- increase in drug abuse
-- increase in the number of homeless people
-- increase in the unemployed
-- increase in malnourished people
-- increase in malignant incurable diseases
-- increase in theft
-- increase in crime
-- increase in homicides
-- increasing the bankruptcies of companies
- reducing the duration of

78 / . Control by the global Yamason mafia elite of each state and its management through the control and management of the special services and secret services of the respective state.

79 / . Control by the global Masonic mafia elite of all Masonic and other and all kinds of Masonic lodges around the world.

80 / . Control and management of the election, election and appointment of presidents, prime ministers, chancellors in the respective countries from the structures of the deep mafia.

81 / . Falsification of the elections in order to win the elections of this party, which is under the rule of global Masonic and mafia elite and the deep state. Managing the election fraud process in countries ruled by the global Masonic mafia elite and the deep mafia.

82 / . The global Masonic mafia elite rules, controls the deep mafia in every country on the planet.

V. . THE DEEP MAFIA AND SCIENCE - ECONOMY

1 / . Funding of scientific teams of economists to impose economic theories and practices in favor of the deep mafia in order to guarantee their profits, enslavement of peoples, countries

2 / . Imposition of economic theories that will guarantee huge profits to the deep mafia.

3 / . Suppression of economic theories and developments that will reveal the essence of the deep mafia

4 / . Suppression of scientists who develop economic theories that contradict the interests and profits of the deep mafia.

5 / . Ignoring scientists who develop economic theories that run counter to the interests and profits of the deep mafia.

6 / . Not allowing such scientists to publish their scientific theories in world-renowned journals.

7 / . Restriction and control and management of publications in world-renowned scientific journals, websites, conferences.

8 / . Preventing the publication of articles and works and scientific theories and works of scientists that contradict the interests and pemaalbs of the deep mafia.

9 / . Suppression in every way economically of the scientists developing economic theories that contradict the interests is the profits of the deep mafia.

10 / . Funding and material support for scientists who create scientific theories that benefit the deep mafia with millions of US dollars

11 / . Funding and material support for the publication of scientific journals that promote and proclaim scientific theories in favor of the deep mafia.

12 / . Funding and material support of NGOs by scientists, sociologists, political scientists, journalists, economists and others who promote and promote scientific theories that benefit the deep mafia.

13 / . Funding and material support of NGOs by scientists, sociologists, political scientists, journalists, economists, who will impose data that will benefit the scientific theories and practices of the deep mafia.

14 / . Financing and material support of media - magazines, newspapers, which will falsify data, trends, and will impose scientific theories and practices that are in favor of the deep mafia.

15 / . Creating strategies and tactics of data falsification, economic data, trends, forecasts, economic practices, management practices by media magazines, newspapers.

16 / . Financing and material support of media - TV CHANNELS, TELEVISIONS, INTERNET SITES, which will promote data, economic data, trends, forecasts, economic practices

17 / . Creating the relevant legislation that imposes the relevant processes, economic processes that are in favor of the deep mafia and its goals for global fascism and global governance.

18 / . Control and management of governments to pursue economic processes that benefit the deep mafia and its goals of global fascism and global governance.

19 / . Control and governance of governments to pursue financial schemes ostensibly to stimulate economic activity and solve global problems, and ultimately ensure the theft of financial resources from companies close to the deep mafia.

The deep state and its representatives act as a shadow government. The deep state does not respect the rights, freedoms, constitutions of the respective state, the treaties for the formation of unions, such as the European Union

In reality, the Deep State uses the following undemocratic models of governance as follows:

- Autocracy
- Oligarchy
- Plutocracy
- Kleptocracy
- Corporatocracy
- Cryptocracy

All these systems of government are governed on the basis of the principles of MAFIOTISM and the Financial Bank Resource Technological Mafia Materialism.

5. Hegel, Marx, Karl Popper, Huntington, Fukuyama, Hayek, Friedman - The ideologues created the ideologies for the GOVERNANCE OF THE ECONOMY AND THE PLANET in order to profit the deep mafia

5.1. Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel and The criticism of Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev to Hegel .

The original ideologist is Hegel. Hegel says: Conflicts create a story.

If conflicts are controlled, managed, and created, what will the story be - induced - generated story. This is stated by Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev as counterpart and critic of Hegel. Finishers and bankers create organize, plan the beginning - the cause, the place of the end of each conflict. The funding of the conflict - both sides.

Existing power is the "thesis" that generates its opposite - "antithesis" The conflict that arises between these two forces creates "synthesis". Conflict conflicts.

The wars represent the synthesis we see according to Hegel's Theory.

Wars create benefits - profit, interest. According to the thesis and the intrigue are necessary for the movement of history. The truth is that both the thesis, the antithesis and the synthesis are important for the capital and the fruits of this capital - the profit.

The trilateral commission openly admits that solving for war and peace is only taken by a few elite people. All property common source - Hegel.

Hegel teaches that the state is God, and the only obligation of the citizens is to serve the state, thus serving God.

Historical dialectics - all historical events emerge from conflicts between opposing forces / thesis and antithesis /, but which are generated by financially resource-based technical mafia-driven materialism, adds Momtchil Dobrev.

That's the real truth.

Supporter and further developed Hegel's theses, but in our opinion, in a very consciously wrong direction that serves the purposes of financially banking, the technically manipulated materialism is fed to Rothschild Karl Marx - a Jew.

Marx and "capital" treat capitalism as a "thesis," communism as "antithesis".

The man who uses Hegel's theses is JM Morgan. JM Morgan studied in 1850 at the Göttingen University in Germany - which center was Hegel's activity. Morgan uses all the parties in his favor. He supports Republicans, Democrats, a Communist Party, and his closest is Julius Hammer, the father of the famous Armand Hammer.

The real theory of Hegel and Marx is the glossy cover that has nothing to do with truth and reality.

The practice is to manipulate people, left, right, centrists, and others.

One of the most prominent figures of modern history that has given its appreciation of the "laws of history" is Karl Marx.

Marx formulated an entirely new historical philosophy that played an important role for billions of people on earth, whom Momtchil Dobrev believed to be deliberately misguided and directed at the masses, with the ultimate goal of manipulating capital and bankers and their benefit from wars, conflicts, and so on.

Actually, according to Momtchil Dobrev, Karl Marx has committed a falsification of history.

The present material proves this - the mistakes and contradictions of Mark and Hegel. Marx is Jewish.

He likes to collect huge amounts of information, but only to use it against his opponents. In the beginning he deals with law and poetry. For years he has been following Hegel's footsteps. Marx behaves like a prophet and thinks in Hegelian categories, establishes those, antitheses and synthesis, without ever giving logical evidence.

He is subordinate to his teacher Hegel.

Makes the same mistakes and adds new mistakes.

Opponents get lowered through several high-spirited words. With his pen, he tries to inspire the masses, constantly dreams of revolutions, and escapes extradition from France. Everywhere he sees the flames of the revolution.

His predictions almost never happen and come true.

Dream and pray for coups and revolutions, but in terms of theory and mafiotismus Financial - Banking Technology Resource mafia-driven Materialismus Lord prof. Momtchil Dobrev each revolution coup and is funded by interested people - ie financiers and bankers ..

5.2/. Karl Marx and the criticism of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev to Karl Marx

The criticism of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev to Karl Marx.

A truly internationally from the 18th century, FINANCIAL BANK RESOURCES TECHNOLOGY MAFFIOTISED MATERIALISM of Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev is working, not the historical materialism of Karl Marx.

Thesis number 1 - at the beginning was matter.

It formulates the principle supremacy of matter without any evidence, and makes conscious misconceptions. Actually based on these theories developed by Lord prof. Momtchil Dobrev - cosmological theory, information theory vortex fields Theory and practice of free energy, Theory of information and energy medicine, Theory of the universe, theory and practice of energy informatonnata genetics , energy-information psychology and energy-information psychiatry, the Spirit-consciousness-the thought is primary. Then is the matter.

Thesis number 2 - BITE DETERMINES CONSCIOUSNESS

Ie. the economic conditions / existence / determine the thinking and the personality of an individual / consciousness.

According to the above-mentioned theories of Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev, the spirit-consciousness-thought determines being, not vice versa.

In 1933, Sigmund Freud criticized Marx. Even the insatiable fact that different people, races and peoples under the same economic conditions behave differently, excludes absolute power from an economic moment. "

On the basis of this "erroneous" theory, Marx develops his historical materialism that only the economy and the ownership of the means of production are decisive.

Historical materialism believes that, ultimately, goods, products, and property determine the course of history, as they promote the social classes.

Created by Lord prof. Momtchil Dobrev banking financial resource tehlogichen mafia materialism prove after a full analysis of the history of finance, the economies of countries around the world since the 13th century, the bankers - financiers and generating psazdavayki conflicts, wars and others make history.

Ie. Prof. Momtchil Dobrev - Halachev's financially-funded, technical, mafia-driven materialism, created by Lord Prof. Momtchil Dobrev-Halachev, is the truth, and the historical materialism of Karl Marx is manipulation.

Thesis number 3 - story is a story of class struggles ..

Marx really believes that all human history can be reduced to class struggles.

Marx sees history only as a history of class struggle, with the exception of prehistory. It distinguishes between individual stages of development.

A truly internationally from the 18th century, FINANCIAL BANK RESOURCES TECHNOLOGY MAFFIOTISED MATERIALISM of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev is working, not the historical materialism of Karl Marx.

Thesis number "4 - the class struggle necessarily leads to the dictatorship of the proletariat, and in the end all classes will be" dashed ".

Historical and Financial Evidence of the Financial Banking Resource Technique of Mafiaized Materialism by Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev.

5.3/. Vladimir LENIN and the criticism of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev to Lenin

Lenin wrote that the only property of matter is to be an objective reality, to exist outside our consciousness.

Matter is a category for characterizing objective reality.

Matter is associated with the social form of movement. These definitions include, in opposition to, at the same time, only meteorology and consciousness.

Lenin emphasized that matter existed until the advent of consciousness. Consciousness possessed only a property similar to absorption, to reflection.

LENIN developed a "law for only the struggle of opposites." He developed the main problems in the theory of knowledge. Lenin developed the doctrine of Marxism on the role of social practice in the theory of knowledge. Lenin pays attention to the historical approach.

He examines thought forms only with content

MATTER AND CONSCIOUSNESS

Dialectical materialism rests on the recognition of the primacy of matter, and that consciousness follows from matter, the Being of methia is absolute. Being determines consciousness.

Matter is uncreative and indestructible and infinite. .

The world is infinitely in time and in space forms of motion of matter.

The problem of the relation of consciousness to matter is a fundamental question in philosophy.

THE THREE BASIC LAWS:

1. LAW ON UNITY AND STRUGGLE OF OPPOSITES. This is the basic law of metropolitanism. Each object contained opposites. By opposites dialectical materialism means:

1.1./ . COUNTRIES IN UNBREAKABLE UNITY

1.2./ . MUTUALLY EXCLUDE EACH OTHER, NOT ONLY IN DIFFERENT, BUT ALSO IN THE SAME RELATIONSHIP

1.3 .. MUTUALLY PENETRATE.

There are no opposites that are not in unity, there is no unity without opposites.

The unity of opposites is relative, temporary, the struggle of opposites is absolute.

According to Prof. Momchil Dobrev, this is a reformulation of Hegel's synthesis of thesis and anti-thesis, which is a development.

It's the same, but in other words.

LAW OF Prof. MOMCHIL DOBREV -

- UNITY, DIFFERENCE and COMPLEMENTARITY.

2. THE LAW ON THE TRANSITION OF QUANTITATIVE ACCUMULATIONS INTO QUALITATIVE CHANGES -. one of the basic laws of dialectics, He explains how and in what way movement and development take place.

Ie the accumulation of imperceptible, gradual quantitative changes at a certain moment for each optedele process, leads to significant, radical, qualitative changes, to a jumpy transition from the old quality to a new one.

Here, according to Prof.. THE DEPENDENCES OF THE FUNCTIONS BETWEEN THE ELEMENTS - IN A NEW WAY - A NEW QUALITY WAY.

3. LAW OF DENIAL OF NEGATION. One of the basic laws of dialectics.

The law expresses the continuity, the connection of the new with the old, the repetition in the higher stage of the development of some properties of the lower stage. . This law justifies the progressive nature of development. In dialectics, the category of negation remains the transformation of one object into another while simultaneously "destroying" the former. But this is such a "destruction" that opens up space for further development and appears as a moment of connection with the preservation of all the positive content of the past stages.

There is really no "destruction". This contradicts the first law.

This contradicts the first law.

4. THE LAW ON GENERAL RELATIONSHIP OF PHENOMENA-

5. LAW ON STATISTICAL AND DYNAMIC REGULARITY.

Contradiction

Universal connection of phenomena

Historical and political

Quality and quantity

Measure

Essence and phenomenon, necessity and chance, volume and content, mediation, reason, attitude, correctness and truth, causality.

5.4./ THE IDEOLOGY OF KARL Poper in favour of the DEEP MAFIA and the criticism of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev to Karl Poper

Soros's ideological platform is from the great Austrian philosopher and thinker Carl Popper who prefers him in London. The idea of freedom aims to create flexible tools for powerful geopolitical influences in the individual countries of East Europe and the developing world. However, we can not only speak of self-presumption of "freedom" as Carl Popper does if these rights of freedom are not based on legal norms, ethical norms, moral norms and society. Otherwise, freedom becomes infinite and chaos of freedom and chaos for freedom.

According to Carl Popper, truth is not something that is discovered, it is invented. Ie. the truth is always temporary, it remains in force until it is rejected. Truth is in the human spirit, in the imagination and the reason of man. The truth, according to Popper, is constantly exposed to the cross-fire of trial and experience - trying to "falsify" it as a substitute, as it has been, and inevitably, progress, civilization, will be inevitable in various stages of human development.

At first, according to Popper, truth is a hypothesis or theory that seeks to solve a question.

The hypothesis or theory is or must be subjected to trial of "experience and error," to testing or rejecting those who are not convinced. All this has an impact on life, causing changes in medical practice, the military industry, public organizations, sex, and others. Until a new theory suddenly appears and does not "falsify" or reject it.

This is Popper's philosophy. It is limited and burdensome.

That truth exists and may have a relative existence does not mean that it is relative. Truth is insecure, so science is vulnerable. But that does not mean that the truth is inaccessible. The existence of truth is evidenced by human progress in all areas: science, technology, society, politics.

Popper turns criticism - ie. the exercise of freedom - the basis of progress. Without criticism, without the possibility to "falsify" all the assurances, there is no progress in science or in the fulfillment of social life.

If people do not have the freedom to question and test the validity of all theories that promise some sort of solution to the questions before them. Everything that promotes Popper is a fiction that does not rest on rational intelligence.

Then, myths, religious and other exhaustions come to be honored instead of rational truths.

. Ie. the exercise of freedom is a fundamental right of reason, of culture, of science.

Popper transforms freedom as a prerequisite for man's life. Popper defines the three worlds: the first world is that of things and material objects, the second is the subjective world of thought, and the third is that of the works of the spirit.

The difference between the second and the third is that the second one is built up of the individual's individual subjectivity of the individual, the ideas, the images, the perceptions, the realms, while the products of the third one, though created by the subjectivity, have become public- scientific institutions, legal institutions, ethical principles, art, culture.

The birth of the critical spirit breaks the walls of the closed society and exposes the person to a full-blown experience: personal responsibility. Freedom, daughter and mother of rationalism and of the critical spirit is a heavy burden on the shoulders of the human being.

Popper says that with the simultaneous birth of the open society, in which intelligence has replaced the irrational, the individual has become a true person in history, and freedom has begun to displace the former bondage.

But here is the criticism of Momchil Dobrev that there can not be just freedom without the legal, ethical, moral norms on which a society is built.

No base, no skeins, no foundation, no building collapses.

Thus, Popper's theory of decay for a "free open society" collapses.

This is a chimera that is used in the wrong direction by Soros and a company.

Soros's ideological platform is from the great Austrian philosopher and thinker Karl Popper, who presupposes it in London. The idea of freedom aims to create flexible tools for powerful geopolitical influences in individual countries in Eastern Europe and the developing world. However, we cannot speak only and arrogantly of "freedom" as Karl Popper does, if these rights to freedom do not rest and are not based on legal norms, ethical norms, moral norms in a society. Otherwise, freedom becomes lawlessness and chaos of freedom and chaos of freedom.

According to Karl Popper, truth is not something that is discovered, it is invented. If the truth is always temporary, it remains in force until it is rejected. The truth is in the human spirit, in the imagination and reason of man. The truth, according to Popper, is constantly exposed to the crossfire of trials and tribulations - they try to "falsify" it to replace it, as has happened and will inevitably happen at different stages of human development, cut progress, civilization.

In the beginning, according to Popper, truth is a hypothesis or theory that seeks to solve a question.

Prof. MOMCHIL DOBREV gives a solution to his criticism of Karl Popper that the truth must be invented.

According to THE THEORY OF THE DEGREE OF TRUTH. THE TRUTH after certain analyzes and availability of new technological, scientific, public discoveries, a REVISION of a GIVEN "TRUTH" is made.

5.5. Francis Fukuyama in February of the DEEP MAFIA and The criticism of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev to Fukuyama

Fukuyama's theory of the end of history is a mixture of Hegelian metaphysics and an imitation of evolutionary theory. According to Fukuyama, liberal democracy is what is called the last form of human government.

For the first time in his book *Identity*, he acknowledges the possibility of liberal democracy falling or regressing.

According to him, liberal democracy has not solved the problem of thymus, which is the part of the soul that wants recognition of its dignity. Isotomy is the desire to be respected on an equal footing with other people. And megalothymia - the desire to be recognized as superior to others..

Modern liberal democracies provide a minimum amount of equal respect, human rights, the rule of law. He says entire countries may feel disrespected, fueling aggressive nationalism.

This is the same for religious believers.

Fukuyama makes no distinction as to which religion is just, which religion does not attack other religions, which religion does not respect other religions, which religion is aggressive against any other faith in order to explain and seek explanations for recognition.

Whether one religion seeks recognition from another religion by recognizing the same religion.

He writes: "There is nothing wrong with the politics of identity itself. It becomes a problem when identity is interpreted or maintained in a certain way.

Identity according to Fukuyama

Identity is a "powerful moral idea." It does not recognize borders and cultures. It is built on the universal thymus of the human psyche. This tells us that we have our own authentic inner self, which is unrecognized.

In the surrounding society was repressive and trembling.

It sharpens our natural desire to recognize our own dignity.

That is, providing us with a means of expressing our resentment when recognition is not received. If this is the basis of the protests, it is directing conflicts of protest on the grounds that someone is not pruned, that he has no dignity.

Fukuyama does not consider the objective conditions of whether there is an opportunity to seek recognition.

Fukuyama does not consider the objective conditions of whether there is a possibility for us to be recognized, who does not allow this, who does not

T.o. it is a proclamation of protest, of an uprising to seek dignity, recognition of one's identity.

Fukuyama erroneously treats liberal democracy, which gives the individual equal rights equal in his freedom, and restricts only current rights in the choice and choice of role in determining his collective political life.

It is limited only to freedom of choice, which is limited and inadequate.

About what is dignity - and it is related to freedoms, morality, moral norms, the principles of statehood, the foundations of moral ethical legal norms of a society.

And they are at the heart of whether and how recognition and dignity and identity are permissible.

Fukuyama views identity very restrictively as a stimulus for protest, for revolution, and so on.

Fukuyama makes an analysis of what freedom is and what is the framework and the minimum elements of freedoms that ensure dignity and recognition of the individual and his identity.

Is the recognition of dignity as an end in itself without considering the legal and moral and ethical framework of a society is an end in itself that Karl Popper is an end in itself and is used by individuals and representatives of the Financial Banking Resource - technological mafia materialism such as George Soros.

Modernization is described as mobile, complex, flexible, and means constant changes and shocks, as well as opportunities that did not exist before.

But freedom and the ability to choose ... can make people feel unhappy and awakened by other human beings.

They may be lured by leaders who tell them that they have been deceived and humiliated by existing power structures,.... "

Loss of status in groups - this is an end in itself and it is not considered from the objective side whether some human groups respect the moral and ethical legal norms of a society, why they do not respect them, why what is the basis of this disrespect, non-recognition of these legal, moral, fluid and norms, what is the purpose of this non-reading - repression, argesia, terrorism.

What is the reason for this disrespect, what are the reasons, the reasons for this disrespect.

Modernity presupposed the existence of a different identity.

It is. opposition of social groups, of ethnic groups, of human societies, groups of ethnic groups, small groups, regional groups because they had a different identity.

Identity is defined by race, gender, job, education, preferences and nationality.

This is a very superficial examination of identity, as it seeks a deliberate division of society into groups by race, gender, stock exchange, even workplace - which is a real prerequisite for using these groups for the purposes of leaders who aim to protest, revolutions, precipices creating between groups in societies, creating conflicts, terrorism, and other aggression.

This is stimulated by aggression - to seek identity.

Without considering whether this identity must comply with the moral and ethical legal norms of development of a society, ie. it is a provocation to protests, terrorism, revolutions, discontent and others.

"The freedom and choices that exist in modern liberal societies can make people feel unhappy and alienated from other human beings."

. However, whether they are freedoms and what, to what extent, to whom, whom, what, to what limits, how is not analyzed by Fukuyama.

What choices are given to people, to what extent, to whom, what, against what, whether equal opportunities are given, to restrict access to these opportunities.

All this is not analyzed by Fukuyama. Is it too simple to analyze freedom, opportunity, dignity,

The request for recognition by a group without whether this request is made in which legal, ethical moral norms in which society is not analyzed.

Too simplistic.

Is loss of status is equipment for protest and other actions and activities.

But what is the status, what are the norms in a society and whether they are decisive is not consciously considered by Fukuyama.

There is even talk of several identities - ie. identity is blurred because it is not viewed through the prism of the rights and freedoms of citizens given to them by a society - by the legal moral, ethical norms of that society. (Everything is blurred to seek conflict,

Is using identity to divide society, the opposition of groups of people with so-called% different identities ".

Is identity is formulated as different, different

Mixed experiences values, desires Experience - Erlebnis mixes and merges with Erfahrung, which is incorrectly scientific. These are different

Mutual respect for dignity is sought without considering the place of man in society in the relevant legal, ethical and moral norms of the respective circumstance and what legal, moral and ethical norms it protects.

Is goals are divided of society, of people into groups of identities, in order to govern these people through these identities

Identity politics is the division of the obstetrics, the joy, the division of people into groups according to my elementary characteristics - benefit, age, race, job, education, profession.

Encouraging the struggle for identity recognition is the same struggle and directing Fukuyama towards new forms of chaos and generating wars. He both cites multiculturalism and insults and calls for building trust in the civic consciousness.

It is not considered through what trap the trust is aimed.

That is why Lord Prof. Dr. Momchil Dobrev Dobrev in 1991. creates a theory of the degree of trust.

Fukuyama sees very little civil liberties and citizenship laws as the basis for identity.

The aim is to respect the basic principles of liberal democracy and to replace the laws of citizenship in the individual member states. I.e. citizenship laws are the only thing necessary for identity according to Fukuyama.

Fukuyama raises the issue of privileging some ethnic groups at the expense of other groups. I.e. it is not considered based on a society - the legal moral, ethical norm and framework of a society, but aims to differentiate, divide, differentiate groups from to ethnic groups.

This is really aimed at conflict, protection of ethnic groups.

I.e. it is mainly the laws of citizenship and not the respect, the application, the reasons for a society.

From what is written that different nations have different identities which leads to different goals and interests, a conflict between different nations and peoples is aimed at.

Fukuyama provides guidance on how European countries to change their identity is a barricade on ethnicity.

I.e. the aim is to create a different identity, to create such identities, which then to oppose other identities, to enter into conflict, into confrontation.

And it focuses on ideological identity.

Here they mix racism,

Equal in opportunities.

It provides guidelines for assimilation to begin in the United States with education.

Too simple to consider citizenship is the right to vote, not other obligations to that society.

It obliges us to owe refugees, understanding, compassion, and support.

But this obligation must also be on the other side, - in the requirement to respect the laws, the legal moral and fluid norms of society.

Too one-sided consideration.

Any non-simple request to address the immigrant problem is called Fukuyama racism.

Inequality. Respect and dignity are seen too simply by Fukuyama.

The term "identity policy" is used to create conflicts between different ethnic groups, rather than analyzing the freedoms given by rights and obligations.

Freedom is not only a right but also an obligation for every human being, when he wants to live he is in a society.

It is no coincidence that Karl Popper views freedom too simply.

Fukuyama does not consider that freedom also means obligations, and these obligations must be fulfilled by the relevant group with the appropriate "identity." I.e. the "identity" stands out and is brought to the forefront and not the rights and obligations under certain freedoms in a society. I.e. the loss of dignity is

And whether a society has the opportunity to respect, recognize, to what extent, how, why the dignity of an individual or group of individuals, but the consideration of Dignity without analyzing in a set of freedoms with their rights and obligations is too simplistic and does not lead to any real results.

Fukuyama does not consider whether the information is available to everyone, how, why, to what extent, or whether it is not electronic.

Fukuyama viewed the revolutions in Georgia too narrowly, the Orange Revolution, the Green Revolution in Iran, the Orange Revolutions in African countries were viewed too simplistically.

Lord Prof. Dr. Momchil Dobrev has analyzed and proved the reasons, the reasons for these revolutions, who caused them, for what purposes, for what reasons, for what purposes, for what money, for what influence, for what invasion in the respective economies and political lives.

The services are being privatized.

Lord Prof. Dr. Momchil Dobrev proved the existence of financial banking resource technological mafia materialism, and what is mafia, its representatives.

Too simplistic Fukuyama speaks of the third part of the soul.

Fukuyama very simplistic mixes soul, sex, race, ethnicity,...

Fukuyama claims that his idea for the end of the story is not understood, one of He claims that it is not a final ending, but a goal.

After Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev understood the historical materialism of Karl Marx and proved that this was not the objective law for the development of a society, but everything was organized by a representative of the financial banking resource technological mafia materialism with the ultimate goal. make money.

Fukuyama argues that liberal democracy is what he calls "the last form of human government." On the other hand, liberal democracy has proved its unsuitability for the development of a civilization.

He now recognizes the possibility of liberal democracies "falling or regressing." Liberal edemocrats did not solve the thymus problem.

According to Fukuyama, the thymus is the part of the soul that wants recognition of dignity.

There is no possibility of recognition.

For Fukuyama, liberal democracy has become unalterable for the West

Fukuyama says democracy needs elites.

HOWEVER, THESE ELITES SERVE THE DEEP MAFIA AND THE GLOBAL MASONIC MAFIOTIZED ELITE.

5.6. Samuel P. Huntington in favor of the DEEP MAFIA and the criticism of Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev to Huntington

Character of the soldiers along the fault line.

According to him, wars occur locally or globally.

At the local level, conflicts arise along the rift between neighboring countries of different civilizations, between different groups of civilizations within a country, and between groups that want to build new states such as Yugoslavia and the former Soviet Union.

At the global level, it provokes conflicts between states - nuclei between the basic states of different civilizations.

He actually uses the telmina civilization to denote one

This is, according to him, the paradigm of "clash of civilizations". He disputes the final history of Francis Fukuyama. Problems of Geopolitical and Sociocultural Problems in his book *The Clash of Civilizations and the Remaking of the World Order* 1996.

He substantiated his thesis that after the end of the Cold War, supranational cultural and religious identities would become the main source of conflict. The term civilizations appeared before 1926. in the book dealing with the Middle East, by Basil Matthews, *Yung Islam of Trek* - This thermis stems from the clash of cultures,. the term was also used by Bernard Lewis in the article "The Roots of Muslim Anger" published in September 1990 in *The Atlantic Monthly* -

Cold peace, Cold war, trade war, quasi-war, difficult peace, strained relations, fierce rivalry, competition, arms race

He makes his own reflections on the various theories and the nature of global policy in the post-Cold War period.

Human rights, liberal democracy, and the capitalist economy are the only ideological alternatives for post-Cold War nations.

Huntington believes that the era of ideology is over, the world has returned to the normal state of affairs, characterized by cultural conflicts.

le His thesis is that the main axis of conflicts in the future will be along the lines of the fault of cultural and religious faults.

Different civilizations have different identities.

Following mainly the construct proposed by Oswald Spengler and Arnold Toynbee, Huntington states that "human history is the history of civilizations." He also classifies the types of civilizations as follows:

- 1 / . Western civilization / based on Catholicism and Protestantism (
- 2 / . Islamic civilization
- 3. Hindu civilization
- 4 / . Chinese civilization / based on Buddhism /
- 5 / . Japanese civilization / based on Shintoism
- 6 / . Latin American civilization / based on Catholicism and local traditions
- 7 / . Orthodox civilization
- 8 / . African civilization

Every civilization wants to preserve its identity.

Most civilizations have a core state, which is dominant and accordingly organizes other states in the respective civilizational community.

According to him, every civilization seeks to preserve its identity, and in many cases to expand the sphere of its influence. According to Huntington, the 21st century will be an era of inter-civilizational clashes or conflicts.

In reality, this is a change in the nature of and the causes of a particular war - be it a cold war, a trade war, a war or others.

There is a blurring of the real causes and established dams of a war, be it any form of it.

This is too simplistic a consideration of the causes of a war.

Talk about the characteristics of the wars along the fault line -

In the first place, community wars are fought between ethnic, religious, racial or linguistic groups.

Since religion is the main defining characteristic of any civilization, wars are always fought between peoples with different religions.

This is a replacement of the truth about who and for what reasons is waging a future war.

What are the motives, what are the reasons for a war, whether and who creates the reason to provoke the war.

The most basic thing is to provoke conflict between different religions, so you can use it to provoke war.

Or to create a front and a war by creating military formations based on a religious foundation like that of ISIL, created by the CIA and supported by the CIA for the conflict in Syria, Libya and other countries.

The establishment of ISIL is aimed at securing and placing a hand in possession of the pipelines from Central Asia to the Mediterranean and the Black Sea.

This is a change in the essence of warfare.

2001 created the new enemy of the United States and the representatives of the Financial - banking resource technology mafia materialized TERRORISM, and a war on terrorism was waged. The identity of the war profiteering is the war on terrorism, which was previously created by the United States and the CIA. and persons of the representatives of this Materialism, in order to conquer markets, resources, technologies and the profit from consumption and trade in these countries.

The ensuing US Trade Wars, US sanctions against Russia and other countries are a real manifestation of these goals and aspirations - for the profits of the representatives of FBRTM Materialism.

All of Huntington's are shattered by Lord Prof. Momchil Dobrev's Theory of Mafiaism and the Financial-Banking Resource Technology Mafia Materialism.

The very creation of the European Union is such a realization of the representatives of this FBRTM Materialism.

5.7. Neoliberalism of Hayek and Friedman in favour of the DEEP MAFIA and CRITICISM to it by Prof. Dr. Momtchil Dobrev

Neoliberalism arose in the 20s and 30s of the 20th century,

The theoretical foundations of neo-liberalism date from classical liberalism of the 19th century.

The economic system is built on the basis of market economy, which is regulated by free competition.

Liberal classics reject the possibility of state intervention.

Neoliberalism recognizes the interference of the state in economic life, but only when the state maintains and works for free competition.

Neoliberalism is the antithesis of the Keynesian economic system - which justifies the need for state intervention in the country's economic life. This theory became dominant in the 30s and 40s after Black Friday, with economic crises in the 70s showing that the state was a weak regulator of economic life.

After World War II, neo-liberalism began to play an important role in Western European countries, and especially in England, / London School /, USA / Chicago School /, Germany / Freiburg School /, France, Italy and Belgium. This is required by the accelerated development of the countries sought after the Second World War.

In the early 1970s, neoliberalism boomed in economic thought. This is after the awarding of Nobel Prizes by economist Friedrich von Hayek and Milton Friedman. This is based on accelerated economic growth. It comes after the state's excessive interference in economic life has been abolished, which is accompanied by all the dangers to freedom that result from it.

Neo-liberals believe that the state is incapable of securing the well-being of all members of society and this necessitates a restriction of its powers.

Hayek and Friedman believe that proportional rather than progressive taxation is a central feature of neoliberalism.

In financial policy, neoliberals maintain the principle of a balanced budget. In the area of monetary policy, the state should be deprived of its monopoly on issuing money.

In the area of social policy, freedom, the enforcement of antitrust laws and consumer protection measures, free initiative, guaranteeing fundamental free citizens should be restricted to a minimum.

The main elements are - priority of private property, low taxes, restrictive social policy, stable money supply, restriction of state intervention in the economy and anti-regulatory.

London School

This school is called "often and neo-Austrian" since the founder of the London School was Friedrich August von Hayek in 1899. , Carl Popper and Linnell Robins.

The concept is for economic development as a spontaneous process, the perception of the economic freedom of individuals and the exclusion of the possibility of state intervention.

According to Hayek, the "spontaneous order" in a market economy is evolutionarily created as an unconscious result of the conscious free actions of individuals.

People are driven by personal incentives to achieve mutual benefit, although no one is guided by thoughts of the good of the community.

According to Hayek, there should be no state intervention in the economy, no protectionist policy,

The state should exercise only administrative functions, with the sole purpose of not infringing on the freedom of individuals, ie. not to violate the interests of capital and labor.

Contradiction. The interests of capital and labor are opposite.

The principles of free competition do not alter the law of supply and demand.

Both supply and demand are managed ie. there is no independence of this law.

Chicago School.

In the 1940s, the neoclassicism trend emerged in the United States as one of the currents of neoliberalism. The founder of neoliberalism in the United States is Milton Friedman, and representatives are Edward Chamberlain, Benjamin Anderson, Maurice Copeland.

The real Keynesian paradigm collapsed in the 1970s,

The ideas of the Austrian School are supported by Ludwig von Mises, Murray Rothbard, Israel Krisner.

Monetarism is the most prominent manifestation of neoliberalism / neo-conservatism / gained influence in the late 1970s and 1980s in the United States. They show the bankruptcy of the Keynesian model, according to which the active intervention of the state is crucial for the stability of the economy.

They believe that there are internal forces for self-regulation of the economy. They argue that there were stabilizing factors governing the economic equilibrium, underlining the fundamental importance of the monetary system in the economic process. According to the monetarists, the high rates of monetary circulation increase caused by the wrong monetary policy were the cause of inflation, cyclical unemployment, and crises in the monetary balance.

Freiburg School

The founder of neoliberalism in Germany is Walter Aiken (1891-1950) - professor of political economy. His supporters are L. Erhard, A. Müller-Armak, V. Röpke, A. Rostov, F. Ben, H. Trossman-Derton. They create some theories, the most famous of which is "social market economy theory".

The economic basis of this economy is the free market based on free competition, which is provided by the state through its legislative powers. They protect free competition. State interventionism in the United States by President Franklin Delano Roosevelt under the so-called "New Deal" is the key to overcoming the Great Depression from 1929 to 1933.

This new course is the real Keynesian model of business functioning. This is, in reality, a type of government - "state - oli-popolistic mafia capitalism".

Neo-liberalism marked its heyday in the 1960s, after economic institutions from London and Chicago identified the institutions critical of the Keynesian model. This is the so-called Chicago School. In reality, this school realizes the ideologies of the financial bank resource technological mafia materialism of Prof. Momtchil Dobrev. His representatives are M. Friedman, F. White, J. Stigler and others.

On the Keynesian model of a set of regulatory measures implemented by the state to stimulate economic activity and business processes, the Chicago School opposes the so-called "clean" market mechanism. They link economic crises with monetary and credit disruptions.

According to them, the most important tool for the state's impact on the economy is the amount of money.

Actually, based on the conclusions of the Financial Banking Technology Mafia driven Materialismus Prof. Momtchil Dobrev, it is evident that in a conscious management of the money supply, crises are created - monetary, economic, financial. Currency crises in which the national currency's exchange rate against the dollar jumps incredibly and really as a result of the depreciation of the national currency.

Simply the scheme of varying the size of the currency - the presence of currency, the retention of currency, the restriction of access to the currency - causes the devaluation of the national currency. Real neo-liberalism, along with neo-conservatism in the 1970s, came to power in the United States through President Ronald Reagan and in the United Kingdom through Prime Minister Margaret Thatcher.

At one point neo-conservatism gives way to neoliberalism. On the basis of globalization, the classic Friedrich von Hayek, a British economist and sociologist of Austrian descent, has been introduced into neoliberalism as the basis of the representatives of the financially resourceful technological mafia materialism of Prof. Momtchil Dobrev in neoliberalism.

In reality, neither "Reaganomics" nor "Thatcherism" forms a neoliberal model of government. In reality, US and UK neoliberalism has emerged as an "export model" implemented through the "Washington Consensus".

The neoliberal model is proving to be a new model for the reborn nomenclature elite - a mechanism for quickly and effectively solving the problem of transferring property from state to private.

In this way, the real representatives of the Financial banking resource technological mafia-driven MATERIALISMUS of Prof. Momtchil Dobrev from the West are aiming for the real economic ruin of the already former adversary - the former socialist countries, with the aim of actually de-colonizing the resources in these countries of the East by these representatives.

In this way Bulgaria was also put into the framework of "neoliberalism".

In reality, the ideology of neoliberalism places at the center of its ideology the "economic man" - calculating, predicting, rationally choosing and knowing his economic interest. On the basis of this view of "economic person" is formed the need for complete freedom of action of this "economic man". In their view, this is a real condition for human progress.

In reality, these individuals associate the freedom of action of an "economic man" with the unrestricted mechanisms of market game.

In reality, this is absolutism.

Market game is really the only condition for development. "There's nothing to sell and anything can be bought.

The question depends on whether there is a search. In reality, the "market game" transcends and replaces the totality of all other human values. Any attempt to seek a unifying human society with ethics and morality is viewed by neo-liberal theorists as a "path to slavery" - according to Friedrich von Hayek.

This paradigm really overturns the whole essence of human society and human essence. In reality, the question of human morality is raised on a market basis - ie. "Anything that is inefficient in the marketplace and does not maximize profit is timeless. According to this ideology, the human and human meter are the sole marketplace.

If the market does not accept an individual, that is, he does not make maximum profit, then this person is not entitled to exist. This makes sense of the whole essence of human society.

ie morality and values are depreciated as anything that has value and value and only sells it. ie The law of supply and demand is really amoral. Because only this is sought and offered which brings money - ie. morality is depreciated. Moral ethical, legal norms are devalued.

ie everything is corrupt.

In our view, however, what is moral and moral is socially just.

This is excluded in neoliberalism - morality, moral norms, legal norms are excluded.

Not everything can be sold, not everything can be offered at any price.

In reality, neo-liberalism was aimed at restricting freedom.

In reality, freedom is associated with being able to offer and seek everything at a certain price. ie this means that morality is offered at a fixed price.

Morality, ethical rules cannot and should not be traded.

Going real with market freedom leads to real slavery of man and everything moral, ethical,

In neoliberalism, it is mainly economic and commercial freedom. It makes growth, development,

Neoliberalism is an ideology and a political agenda and system that outstrips free markets. Every battle against neoliberalism is seen as a battle against free markets.

But who owns the "free markets" and are they "free"?

Markets are not free at all since they are dominated by huge companies that impose their marketing and branding strategies, impose their prices, increase their business, conquer more and more territories and leave no free territory for competition.

There is really no competition.

For example, is it competition in Bulgaria - like German supermarket chains and superstores - sells products manufactured in Bulgaria at 4 times higher prices than those sold by these Bulgarian producers - with a foreign owner in foreign markets - Angolan and German. Is this a limited competition?

There is really no access to markets, no real competition, there are imposition of marketing, branding strategies, product promotion strategies. , prices, goods, services.

Actually who owns the market, he also owns the income of the population.

There is a real dominance of certain companies in certain markets. Neoliberalism really has nothing to do with free markets. All these are words and words to manipulate.

ie there is a conduct of the public system in the name and for the benefit of the market;

There is a real, forced, undemocratic and unequal reorganization of the foundations of a society.

What is achieved:

- Intensification and extenzification
- Enhancing, accelerating, differentiating differences
- Strengthening, accelerating, segregating inequalities
- Strengthening, accelerating the separation of the debt spiral and impoverishment
- Reinforce, accelerate division

Not fair distribution of public goods.

At the core are global corporations that manage, create, control, market and price within it with the ultimate goal of maximizing profits, draining all the population.

Neoliberalism is a deliberate act to subvert the moral ethical rules of law in order to cause a loss of judgment against the law.

According to neoliberalism, human beings are a calculator of profits and losses.

Moral ethical norms are ignored and the goal is to weaken the welfare state and any commitment of the state to the people.

Neoliberalism is a method of rearranging human society. Neoliberalism makes every person think of themselves as the owner of their knowledge and initiative, talents, to compete and to constantly adapt. Relations between people are no longer seen as competition alone. Neoliberalism regards competition as the only legitimate organizational principle of human society and human activity.

The market is the sole appraiser of the qualities of man, his worth and the sole guardian of human freedom. This system of evaluating the quality of each person in terms of price and value actually produces a small part - a caste of winners and a huge army of losers only.

Hayek believes that it solves the problem of modernity, the problem of operational knowledge. According to Hayek, the market legitimizes the trade in goods and services with precisely defined prices and value for the qualities of the human personality, but the market only reveals the truth.

The reverence for the free market causes the values of the human being and the human personality, which have no price and cannot be sold, to be erased.

This is a real creation of a new world - a world governed by the rich only for their benefit and profit.

According to Hayek, the market can be considered a kind of consciousness.

While Adam Smith thinks that the market can only be justified in the light of individual values, the virtues of the human personality, he is real concerned that when society rests and develops solely on self-interest, it will not be human society.

Hayek is considered the forerunner of neoliberalism, which reduces everything to a market and economy, to goods and services of prices and values. Hayek considers the price system on the market as reason and the only reason that is effective, logical, useful to society. Hayek structures the whole reality on the model of economic competition and the supply and sale of goods and services only at a certain value and price.

But to transform human values as goods and services at a certain price, it embodies the real human essence and is only the prerogative of the rich and the oligarchy which aims only at profit regardless of the value of human life. Hayek considers and believes that every human activity is conscious and only then valuable when it has economic value and cost. Human activities can be brought to the basic concept of wealth, value, price, exchange, cost and above all price. Prices are a means of effectively allocating scarce resources, considerations, needs, and benefits.

Human activities and qualities must be cost and value. Prices are determined by supply and demand. For a market to function well, it must be free and competitive.

Civil society, human values, moral values, ethical values of man, free institutions freedom of conscience, honor, dignity, religion, the press find no place in Hayek's thinking. According to Hayek, only the market provides the only protection of society against totalitarianism. In order to prevent totalitarianism, the state must only guarantee market freedom. These are just thoughts. While in liberalism the state must leave the traders of peace, in neoliberalism the state must be active in organizing free markets. It is the state that must constantly maintain market freedom.

Everything should be based on economic values and analysis. On the other hand, the state should leave sufficient autonomy on the market, so as not to disturb the natural functioning of the markets.

Therefore, ideally, the state provides conditions - a neutral, independent, fixed, universal legal framework in which market forces to act spontaneously arise.

The price system is the one that manages and manages the market of everything.

According to Hayek, the free market left on its own mechanisms, with its price system, acts as a reason. Ie the market calculates what individuals cannot realize. The market values people with their prices and values.

According to Hayek, the market is a means of knowing. Such a market is not a human invention, and it can be manipulated like anything else.

Hayek does not even consider the possibilities of market manipulation and its prices.

He doesn't even look at it, he doesn't even mention it.

This is not accidental. These are the means of monopolies, of the originality, which uses manipulation to control, create, control the market and its prices.

The sole public purpose is to maintain the market itself.

Again, this is for the sole benefit of monopolies and oligarchy.

The market is the only legitimate form of knowledge. At the individual level, our values are only personal, they are just an opinion that does not need to be accepted.

Values that have no value and price are not respected.

It is no coincidence that Ronald Reagan and Margaret Thatcher are the proponents of Hayek's neo-liberalism; this proved their support for the monopolies and the oligarchy that governs the states, with the ultimate goal of governing, creating, marketing, setting rules, pricing values and winning.

Thatcher praised Hayek and promised to unite his free-market philosophy with the revival of Victorian values: family, community, hard work. But I really forget that. Neoliberalism is really at the heart of any crisis, especially the crisis of 2007-2008. Profits and transfers of money into offshore accounts and zones.

Real neoliberalism is at the root and cause of the collapse of public health, education, child poverty, ecosystem collapse,

Inequality is a virtue, the market guarantees that every person receives what he or she deserves, depending on its price and value.

For neoliberalism, competition is the most important characteristic of human relationships.

Real neoliberalism defines citizens as consumers whose choice is determined by buying and selling. It is the market that rewards human quality and punishes its inefficiency. According to Hayek, the market provides benefits that have accrued by accident not going as planned. The real restriction of competition is imprisonment. Taxes and regulations should be minimized. Public services must be privatized. According to neoliberalism, collective agreements and the actions of trade unions distort the market. The market is determined by a hierarchy of winners and losers.

Inequality is a generator of wealth and a reward for utility.

It is the market that guarantees and provides everyone with what they deserve.

On the one hand, the poor blame themselves and, according to neoliberalism, they must blame themselves for not being successful, not being effective, not being useful.

Being unemployed means that the person is not enterprising, useless, has no real value and cost to look for.

In a world governed only by competition and the market, those who are unsuccessful must look for the blame alone, and therefore they are the losers.

The term neoliberalism occurs in 1938. at a meeting in Paris, attended by two of its representatives Ludwig von Mises and Friedrich Hayek.

In *The Road to Slavery*, published in 1944. Hayek argues that "governmental planning by crushing individualism will inevitably lead to totalitarian control. This is similar in Mises' book *Bureaucracy*.

Most of all, the titles of these books attract the attention of rich people who are beginning to finance these theses. Hayek began to establish a transatlantic network of academics, businessmen, journalists and wealthy business activists.

While Hayek believes that governments must regulate competition in order to prevent monopolies from forming, he is inferior to Milton Friedman, believing that monopoly power should be seen as a remuneration for efficiency.

Hayek introduces the quota theory of spontaneous order in the market.

Ludwig von Mises and Friedrich von Hayek did not cease to be critical of the mainstream economy, even between the 1930s and 1970s. The economic crisis of the early 1970s gave rise to a new look at monetary theory and the theory of the economic business cycle. Therefore, they are looking for solutions that respond to unexplained processes that include high inflation and low employment.

The turning point came in 1974 when Friedrich von Hayek was awarded the Nobel Prize in Economics with his work on monetary theory and the theory of the economic business cycle.

Hayek's analysis begins with the market. For Hayek, the market is an institution of spontaneous public order. Free spontaneous markets and free will are interconnected and conditioned. According to Hayek, "freedom is a situation in which individuals are not dependent on the arbitrariness of others. 1948

For Hayek, information and knowledge play an important role, they are the main drivers of market processes. There is no perfect information available to match the expectation with reality. According to Hayek, personalities adapt

to the market and improve conditions for themselves by improving the knowledge and information available through the market itself.

Regulation must only be done through the market itself and the market itself.

Hayek develops a theory of equilibrium in the market of Leon Vapras, who assumes that it is aesthetics with perfect knowledge of market players.

According to Hayek, balance is a dynamic category due to incomplete awareness.

But this lack of awareness is managed and controlled by monopolies and the oligarchy, which does not allow full market awareness.

It is the Mafia that controls the market's distortion. It makes awareness.

The discrepancy between search and supply and because of incomplete information and incomplete market information.

The Mafia manages the flow of information. The Mafia owns the information, there is no perfect information, they hide the information, they restrict access to information, they restrict information.

According to representatives of the Austrian School, money is what causes supply and demand imbalances and is a generator of cyclical fluctuations.

Controlling the amount of money supply can avoid cyclicity in crises.

Hayek, however, emphasizes more on the secondary effect of the monetary policy of the government, namely the discrepancy between the structure of production and the inclinations for savings in society.

The Stagflation Depression of 1972 Hayek explains with a disturbance of the dynamic equilibrium in the structure of production.

Changes in the supply of money by the central bank have a real impact on the market economy.

Money is the one that causes a mismatch between the search and the marketing.

According to Prof. Dr. Momtchil Dobrev, the availability of free money from profits from non-productive activities - trade services and others generate crises.

Neo-liberalism through globalization guarantees the management of the market by monopolies and oligarchy.

The cyclical destabilization, which is the result of the monetary policy of central authorities, influences the change in the structure of production, which is incompatible with the specific norm of saving in society. The change in the money supply by each central bank has an impact on the structure of production, trade, consumption, and savings. Money is the one that causes a mismatch between supply and demand in the economy. Wrong information, marketing of wrong information.

The creation of capital goods is achieved.

The market calculates all unprofitable productions through deflation.

Secondary deflation leads to a loss of confidence.

Neoliberalism leads to a setback on social and economic benefits.

Neoliberalism puts at the top of society's existence - individual freedoms that do not obey any rules.

This is completely wrong because order in a social society is provided by ethical, moral, legal norms.

It is no coincidence that 5th century BC, Hammurabi introduced moral, ethical and legal norms into the laws that govern a society.

According to another neo-liberal representative, Milton Friedman, inflation was a monetary phenomenon. These words rest on the faith of the power of the central banks for more than 30 years.

In reality, Milton Friedman gives central banks the power to govern societies. - this proves that Milton Friedman really protects the representatives of Prof. Momchil Dobrev's Financial Resource Technology Mafia Materialism whose sole purpose is huge profits, the enslavement of entire nations and peoples to work for them, a real slavery.

According to Milton Friedman, the money supply of money by central banks determines the price of money. However, if the bankers act properly there will be no inflation or deflation and the economy will only grow smoothly.

Actually, the value of money depends on the amount of money put into circulation.

Organizing currency - currency in circulation and access to currency - leads to inflation and devaluation of the currency in question - George Soros systems are examples.

However, money is not a commodity like any other in terms of production value in supply and demand. It is money that measures and measures units of everything.

It is a lie that increasing or decreasing money supply cannot lead to inflation.

Milton Friedman's monetary theory presents the following basic principles:

- The free market is a stable self-regulating system that loses its stability in every state impact
- The state should not be allowed to produce material assets, regulate employment and prices

- Floating exchange rates are preferable to fixing, because the fixed rates create a black market and a large amount of transactions are made there
- In order to stimulate production, it is necessary to maintain a constant low rate of increase in the amount of money in circulation
- Change in the amount of money in circulation with the main reason for changes in nominal income
- Unemployment, inflation, stagnation and more are all caused by wrong government policies
- Government measures aimed at redistributing income through progressive taxation are economically inefficient
- The government is needed as a means of determining the rules of the game, and is a judge who interprets the established rules and enforces them.
- Continued inflation is the result of printing too much money
- Restricting the use of monetary policy to stimulate the economy
- The implementation of shock therapy - full privatization, free trade and government spending cuts, deregulation
The quantity of money has no relation to their quality - their purchase value.

Inflation has been a matter of balance between market demand and supply and the expectations of business in government. Economic growth is a kind of perpetuum mobil and self-organizing by itself. As higher expectations of the business lead to more investments that support consumption and increase inflation expectations. Market balloons inflate as final demand begins to fall behind as investment rises. Deflation is the opposite. The inflation spurt, as well as the hyperinflation of the Friedman compound, are made possible when the economy as a whole has no balance between supply and demand.

Here is the criticism of Prof. Momchil Dobrev that investment is not leading to production and investment in production.

According to Friedman, an increase or decrease in money supply alone cannot trigger inflation.

Prof. Momchil Dobrev's practice and experience and findings and conclusions show exactly the opposite - that managing cash resources, blocking cash, leads to hyperinflation.

After Margaret Thatcher and Ronald Reagan came to power, the introduction of the other components followed as follows:

- Tax relief for the rich, oiling up of unions, deregulation of everything, privatization, outsourcing, and competition for public services.
- Through the policies of the IMF, the World Bank, the Maastricht Treaty and the World Trade Organization, the full range of policies of neo-liberalism is imposed, especially without democratic consent and force on the whole world. in USA.
- Chile is the first country to adopt new "no alternative" policies that promote freedom and choice. The program of neo-liberalism is fully implemented in Chile. However, freedom concerns only the rich, but not the poor.
- Freedom from union and the lack and dismantling of collective bargaining, the signifier of neoliberal liberty.

Freedom means :

- Reducing pay levels,- No regulation,- Accrual of huge interest rates,- Exotic financial instruments.
- From taxes,- Freedom from distribution of goods,- Financial speculation,- Free movement of capital
- Freedom of money and money laundering

Milton Friedman and Ludwig von Hayek advocate the use, challenge, and recovery of crises. They consider crises as a method of healing and creating new conditions.

Where neo-liberalism may not impose principles and programs and policies, it is compelled by so-called WTO trade agreements by imposing a system of investor-state dispute settlement through offshore arbitration tribunals whereby corporations can coerce countries to repeal social, environmental and other protections and regulations. This is all done to the benefit of international corporations and the international oligarchy. In this way, states are robbed of corporations. In reality, democracy is devoid of face.

The requirement of neoliberalism for the state is to impose universal competition. Actually, all water management utilities are being privatized,

However, according to Prof. Momchil Dobrev, crises are a real system and management of middle-class robbery and 99% of the population of a country.

Inequalities in the distribution of goods and the wrong distribution of goods cause the rich to become richer and the poor to multiply. By privatizing or marketing publicly-traded services that distribute public goods such as electricity, heating, water, trains, healthcare, education, roads, prisons, it allows corporations that privatize them or who receive management concessions to set the prices they want, economically unreasonable and thus pricing - incredibly high

somewhere with a 500-800% increase, with corporations actually setting up cash desks to ask for prices that are not actually made. Is this income actually unprocessed. This is real non-interest income. Like the interest in the banks, there is an unearned income.

The corporations that have privatized such public services are amassing enormous wealth. There, the profit margins are thousands of percent. This can be seen, for example, in the United Kingdom, India, Russia, and Mexico.

The rich actually manage and control money as another asset. They earn unprocessed income from this asset.

For the last 40 years, there has been a process of shifting the wealth from those who create new products and goods to those rich who only control and manage money and earn a non-working income - the interest on money. Revenue earned is replaced by unearned income.

Bank failure is paid by the state, ie. from the people. The profit remains for the business and the rich, and the risk remains for the state - for the people.

Governments privatize public services, deregulate corporations, regulate citizens, bring down the health care system, pensions, education.

In reality, this is also the case in politics, as large groups of the population are manipulated to manipulate their voting rights.

In reality, there is a kind of totalitarian rule, in which the state forces the people to obey it in whatever pleases the rich.

Through the freedom of movement of capital, goods, people, the conquest of markets, whole countries by multinational companies and corporations, by financial mastodons, becomes real. One model by which capital liberalization is used for product trading is the franchising model of conquering markets, countries, countries of international corporations. In reality, Friedman's book *The Road to Slavery, Bureaucracy, or Capitalism and Freedom* is nothing new, since the interests of the rich to conquer and occupy the world and to gain gains from the new globalized order are clearly and proven.

In reality, these roads are roads to power.

Another form of seizure of public assets is the creation of public - private partnerships between the state and international corporations, even in areas such as defense and weapons development, in the field of security.

Public - private partnerships emerged in the 1980s and especially in the 1990s. In this way, the state or local government assigns tasks to the private sector, which in reality, however, enjoy huge profits, so that, if there are even losses, the state will pay them, exaggerate the costs and values of their investments in infrastructure.

The lack of oversight and control makes the whole process unmanageable, where profits are huge and any information leakage is "commercial confidentiality".

Private companies entering the defense and security sector actually began in January 2001 to take place after the September 11, 2001 event. , under the "war on terror" thesis, such public - private partnerships are created with the ultimate goal of securing huge profits for private corporations paid by the state. The real invasion of foreign countries by these public-private partnerships and the invasion of privacy of citizens provides trillions of dollars in business. This is a business for terrorism - the market for terrorism with the ultimate goal of making huge profits. This displaces and replaces war as a system for providing huge profits. The real result is coercion, lack of democracy, repression, inequality, widespread control and repression. These PPPs actually participate in wars, conquer countries act across borders, actively participate in hostilities, seize resources, drain resources.

In the end, after the 2008 financial crisis, the blame was shifted to change capitalism and financial institutions, and the change in government and blame was transferred to the state, not the real guilty. Finally, after 2008, constitutional and legal changes were introduced that obliged states to change in the name and for the benefit of financial institutions. In addition, laws were adopted to criminalize freedom of assembly and protest to restrict citizens' rights. Such laws were adopted in 2015 in Spain, Canada.

One example in the US is the crackdown on Occupy activists.

The crackdown on protests in Turkey in 2013, the massacre in Mexico in 2014, South Africa's 2012.

Real neoliberalism is an ideology that actively promotes the forced, non-democratic and inequitable reorganization of society solely for the benefit of the rich.

There is a real undermining of citizens' social and police rights.

Since 2001, a merger of power, business and security has actually taken place.

In the name of the economic need for the profits of the rich, the democratic rights of citizens are curtailed.

In reality, there is justification for violence and repression in the name of "democracy".

The state is no longer the embodiment of the will of the people, but of corporations, business, the mafia.

The conclusions of Prof. Momchil Dobrev are as follows: Not only monetary policy but also free money received from profit from non-productive activity - and especially from activities in trade, profits from sale of military equipment, profits from non-productive activities - such as trade - the most -more with high rates of profit, profits from speculation, profits from financial activity, profits from trading the liberating huge money supply that is realized in such industries where the profits are huge - at least 300 - 800 percent and one - two years - which is the construction, drugs,

Encouraging monetary policy activity produces good results in the short term but not in the long term.

The basic interest rate is the main source of information for each market entity.

This source of information really distorts the expectations and preferences it gives to the supply and demand.

VI. . Principles of FINANCIAL BANK RESOURCE TECHNOLOGICAL MAFIA – DRIVEN MATERIALISMUS - THE IDEOLOGY OF THE DEEP MAFIA

The only goal is the profit and enslavement of peoples, states, governments, the creation of monopolies.

Participating countries - banks, financial institutions, companies - oil, resource, for the production of steel, oil, food, medicine, fuels. Finance and money determine politics, wars, peace.

Primary goal and approach: Establishment of central banks in the countries - the big countries that can really control not only the finances but also the economic activity and the policy. Through these central banks will be controlled governments, states, parties, citizens, a whole territory, in terms of money, investment, resources, use, in whose favor and for what.

These are the initial steps. Formation of central banks in the countries - the big countries, which can really control not only the finances but also the economic activity.

Establishment of central banks in the states, owned by private individuals and private banks. In this way the economies of these states, the governments of these states, over citizens, over entire societies are controlled. Where the creation of central private banks in the countries is not allowed - occasions are generated to provoke civil wars, wars between countries, provoking "revolutions", - their financing by the bank-financial resource-technological capital. Creating conditions for destabilization of the respective country, import of corruption, provocation of civil war, provocation of war, creation of conditions for maturing of economic crisis, which will lead to destabilization of the political power in the country. Generating and provoking wars, conflicts, fictitious conflicts, financing both warring parties with loans - with the ultimate goal of profit, borrowing, and then giving loans to rebuild these countries, giving loans to rebuild the economies of the warring countries, usurpation of companies managing resources - oil, gold, trade, medicines, food, creation of a military situation - closing - institutional occasion. System: Financing on both sides waging war between them. In practice, the countries owe money to the banks, then the banks and financial institutions finance the recovery of the economies of these countries. The profits are huge. The rate of return on weapons and ammunition is the highest and the fastest return and turnover. They finance the supply of arms, ammunition, food, clothing, ammunition, additional equipment, and actually manage the war process - when to have an advantage for one country, when for the other. In reality, with the supply of weapons and ammunition, they control the process of war - which country should take the lead and when and for how long.

Purpose:

Control of governments - not only through finances, but also the cultivation of loyal government and state subjects - from universities, secular institutions, clubs, lodges, foundations, which then or become presidents, prime ministers, ministers, heads and important departments .

Control of the security services and mastery of the compromising material.

Control of entire countries

Through debt securities control governments, states.

Control of money, their circulation, movement, direction, direction.

Policy control and implemented policies

Press control

Policy control

Control of Masonic lodges

Meaning and purpose of war, military conflict, aggression - profit.

Control and prevention of the introduction of technologies.

Control and prevention of the production of technologies and free energy to be used by all people and nations.

Control of patents that contribute to the development of civilization, not to see the light of day, to be forgotten, not to be used.

Control and liquidation of scientists who have created innovative solutions for the benefit of mankind in science, technology, treatment.

Control and prevention of the production of developments for the treatment of deadly diseases.

Import and export of corruption in a country as a result of its destabilization.
Import of terrorism.
Export and import of mafia principles in one country
Debt economics, money control. He who controls money controls states, societies, peoples, governments.
Possession of the masses, peoples, personalities.
Personality control, with debit, credit cards, mobile phones, mobile applications - continuous control. stta.
Control of the civil society through foundations - the NGOs in order to replace the public opinion, their financing for the purpose of control and management of the society.
Possession not all resources of the earth, oil, gold, silver, uranium and income from them.
Disease management through diseases.
Population management through environmental pollution
Technology management, when one technology to be implemented, why not, to keep another, to disappear.
Private repositories of huge treasures.
Generate crises - all kinds, economic, currency, social, refugee, conflicts, wars, political crises. The financial crisis occurs the fastest, the currency crisis occurs instantly, followed by economic crises, Part of the financial crisis and one type of it is the currency crisis. A financial crisis follows. Economic crises always follow.
World currency controlled by members.

Crisis generation schemes:

- Concluding wars
- Concluding military conflicts
- Concluding military intervention in a country
- Import and export of corruption, of mafia,
- Dtraction of money from circulation immediately creates economic crises. They, in turn, cause enormous damage to entire countries. Accordingly, he receives loans.
- Refugee crisis - caused - creates economic, social, demographic, social, political crises.
- Cautioning a financial crisis
- Concluding a currency crisis
- Concluding economic crises
- Provoking a political crisis - not always in the last place
- Increasing the deficit - in order to support
- World wars are becoming redundant due to the danger of nuclear exchange, so terrorism will be used.
- Managing the population through fear. Instilling fear among the population.
- Creating an antipode - through fear, manipulation,
- Creating a machine for intrigue
- Creating a machine for apparent occasions - for wars, conflicts, aggression, sabotage,
- Concluding inflation and deflation afterwards
- Creation of an antipode - with the ultimate goal of the battle of the Cold War - huge profits are generated, huge cash flows,
- Ownership of resources
- The machine of intrigue and compromising and creating false occasions.
- Generating, financing and combating terrorism.

- FORMULA OF THE MAFIOTISMUS

The most simple model of the mafia which describes the factors which influence about the amount, type, and etc, of the mafia is the following:

MAFIOTISMUS = PERSONAL / GROUP/ hidden or open / Power / on the top of the state institutions / state and etc/ + Influence + Connections / to personal, private companies + Interests / personal, private, corporative / + ORDER / ORDERS + Personal Management of all state neveaus + Personal Control of all state niveausMafia structure /inside of or outside / + Monopoliy Riegths + laws / rules / practices / procedures + possibility of taking an alternative decision - obligation - responsibilities - morality / ethics + Personal management and personal control of distribution of public state monetary and other resources / state funds and funds /.

FIELDS OF GOVERNMENT OF THE MAFIA IN MAFIOTISMUS

The mafia can be found in all spheres of public life.

Areas of manifestation of the mafia through the mafia are: -1 / . The sphere of state administration. This includes government, government departments and institutions, local authorities and others, - 2 / . The sphere of politics-. This includes parliament, political parties, trade unions, movements, business and non - profit associations,. The sphere of

the judicial system / judges /, - 4 /. The sphere of the law enforcement institutions / prosecutor's office, investigation services, police /, -5 /. The sphere of public services - healthcare, education, social assistance, etc., - 6 /. The sphere of the private sector,. The sphere of the media / radio, television, newspapers, magazines and other media /, - 8 / The sphere of the "civil sector" / civil associations, non-governmental organizations and others /

VII. Does the Nobel Committee serve the DEEP MAFIA in the economics awards?!?!

This is a question for readers, because above in the article we proved how the deep mafia creates inequalities and uses economic theories and practices for profit.

Below we quote the subjects for which the Nobel Prizes in Economics have been awarded, which complements the conclusion that science is being done in favor of the deep mafia and it is fully supported.

So the reader himself can answer the question:

Does the Nobel Committee serve the DEEP MAFIA in the distribution of Nobel Prizes in economics?!?! !!

Here are the topics and developments for which the Nobel Prizes in Economics have been awarded

"for having developed and applied dynamic models for the analysis of economic processes"

"for the scientific work through which he has developed static and dynamic economic theory and actively contributed to raising the level of analysis in economic science"

"for his empirically founded interpretation of economic growth which has led to new and deepened insight into the economic and social structure and process of development"

"for their pioneering contributions to [general economic equilibrium theory](#) and welfare theory."

"for the development of the input-output method and for its application to important economic problems"

for their pioneering work in the [theory of money](#) and economic fluctuations and for their penetrating analysis of the interdependence of economic, social and institutional phenomena."

"for their contributions to the theory of [optimum allocation](#) of resources"

"for his achievements in the fields of [consumption](#) analysis, monetary history and theory and for his demonstration of the complexity of stabilisation policy"

"for their pathbreaking contribution to the theory of [international trade](#) and international [capital](#) movements"

for his pioneering research into the [decision-making](#) process within economic organizations"

"for their pioneering research into economic development research with particular consideration of the problems of [developing countries](#)."

"for the creation of [econometric](#) models and the application to the analysis of economic fluctuations and economic policies"

"for his analysis of [financial markets](#) and their relations to expenditure decisions, employment, production and prices"

"for his seminal studies of industrial structures, functioning of markets and causes and effects of [public regulation](#)"

„for having incorporated new analytical methods into economic theory and for his rigorous reformulation of the theory of [general equilibrium](#)"

"for having made fundamental contributions to the development of systems of [national accounts](#) and hence greatly improved the basis for empirical economic analysis"

"for his pioneering analyses of [saving](#) and of [financial markets](#)"

"for his development of the contractual and constitutional bases for the theory of economic and political [decision-making](#)"

"for his contributions to the theory of economic growth"

"for his pioneering contributions to the theory of markets and [efficient utilization of resources](#)"

"for his clarification of the probability theory foundations of [econometrics](#) and his analyses of simultaneous economic structures"

for their pioneering work in the theory of [financial economics](#)"

"for his discovery and clarification of the significance of [transaction costs](#) and [property rights](#) for the institutional structure and functioning of the economy"

"for having extended the domain of microeconomic analysis to a wide range of [human behaviour](#) and interaction, including non-market behaviour"

"for having renewed research in [economic history](#) by applying economic theory and quantitative methods in order to explain economic and institutional change"

for their pioneering analysis of equilibria in the [theory of non-cooperative games](#)."

"for having developed and applied the hypothesis of [rational expectations](#), and thereby having transformed [macroeconomic analysis](#) and deepened our understanding of economic policy"

"for their fundamental contributions to the economic theory of incentives under asymmetric information"
"for a new method to determine the value of [derivatives](#)."
"for his [contributions](#) to [welfare economics](#)"
"for his analysis of [monetary](#) and [fiscal policy](#) under different [exchange rate](#) regimes and his analysis of optimum currency areas"
"for his development of theory and methods for analyzing selective samples"
"for his development of theory and methods for analyzing [discrete choice](#)"
"for their analyses of markets with [asymmetric information](#)"
"for having integrated insights from psychological research into economic science, especially concerning human judgment and decision-making under uncertainty"
"for having established laboratory experiments as a tool in empirical economic analysis, especially in the study of alternative market mechanisms"
"for methods of analyzing economic [time series](#) with time-varying [volatility \(ARCH\)](#)"
"for methods of analyzing economic time series with common trends ([cointegration](#))"
"for their contributions to dynamic macroeconomics: the time consistency of economic policy and the driving forces behind [business cycles](#)."
for having enhanced our understanding of conflict and cooperation through [game-theory](#) analysis."
"for his analysis of intertemporal tradeoffs in [macroeconomic](#) policy"
for having laid the foundations of [mechanism design](#) theory"
"for his analysis of trade patterns and location of economic activity"
"for her analysis of economic governance, especially the commons"
"for his analysis of economic governance, especially the boundaries of the firm"
"for their analysis of [markets with search frictions](#)"
"for their empirical research on cause and effect in the macroeconomy"
"for the theory of stable allocations and the /practice of market design."
"for their empirical analysis of asset prices."
"for his analysis of market power and regulation".
"for his analysis of consumption, poverty, and welfare".

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

In this article we prove and show that the ideology of the deep mafia is mafia and the financial banking resource technological mafia-drivejn Materialismus, created.

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